

EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS FOR ENHANCEMENT OF SURFACE ROUGHNESS OF CNC TURNING BY B₄C TOOL

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Abstract-

CNC is now a day's plays a vital role in industry. This papers deals with the parametric effects such as spindle speed (1500-2100 rpm) (N) (X1), depth of cut (DOC) (.15-.55 mm) (X2) and feed rate (f) (30-50 mm/min) (X3) on machining characteristics of surface roughness (Ra) during fabrication of IS-617 Aluminum miniature component by advanced CNC lathe using Boron-carbide tool. The article analyzes the second-order mathematical model development with co-relation of co-efficient of regression and analysis of variances (ANOVA) using desirability function analysis (RSM) during the production of the miniature segment. The article also consists of single-objective optimization for achieving the optimal parametric combination for minimum surface roughness for this manufacturing operation. Also multi-objective optimization analysis for tool wear and surface roughness has been performed. The project also shows the fabricated micro-product of Aluminum at the optimal parametric conditions using CNC programming.

Keywords- CNC, Boron-carbide, SR, Turning, Optimization.

1. Introduction

CNC Lathe is a highly advanced machine-tool which is involved now a day for production and fabrication of precise job with higher accuracy. Some of the researchers used various optimization processes and algorithms during straight turning by CNC Lathe. Optimization of process parameters helped for findings acceptable results during machining operations [1-2]. The surface roughness of job specimens was the key factor to maintain the product quality as well as manufacturing cost [3]. The formation of irregularity on the job depended on process parameters [4-5-6]. Upadhyay et al. [7] were used acceleration amplitude of vibration in axial, radial and tangential direction for reducing the surface irregularities. Moriwaki [8] applied the pattern recognition process to identify the states of cutting during CNC turning. Dhabale et al. [9] developed mathematical models for the rate of material removal and surface roughness. K.palani kumar et. al.[10]reported thatfeedrateistheparameterwhichhasgreatereffectonsurfaceroughness, followed by cutting speed and % volume fraction of SiC in machining of Al/SiC particulate composites using response surface methodology. Sahin and Motorcu [11] mathematical model was developed of surface roughness factor for turning of mild steel using coated carbide tools and RSM was applied. They reported that feed rate was main effecting parameter on the surface roughness. They found that with increasing feed rate surface roughness increased where it decreased with increasing depth of cut and speed. From all parameters depth of cut was significant compared with cutting speed. By Noordin et al. [12] the coated carbide tools performance has been described by response surface methodology though the turning of AISI1040 mild steel. They reported that feed rate is the most important parameter effecting the surface roughness and tangential force. By Sing and Kumar [13]the optimization of feed force has been studied though selection of process parameters that is to say feed, speed, and depth of cut in turning of EN24 steel using TiC coated tungsten carbide as a tool materials. Taguchi method was

used by researcher and reported that the feed force were affected by variation of depth of cut and feed as compare to speed. The TLBO algorithm was used for CNC turning for optimization of the process parameters [14]. But most of the researchers used boron carbide tools or stainless steel tools and not applied their findings in production or fabrication of miniature components as well as in the manufacturing of products.

To date more research gap is found about CNC lathe operations, the objective of the present research has been drawn out to reach the objective of the research. Desirability function analysis has been performed to satisfied the second-order mathematical models, correlating with ANOVA test and multi-response optimization during fabrication of miniature products with high precession and less tool wear rate the findings have been applied to produce a tiny product that can enthusiasts the researcher and scientist to reach the goal.

2. Materials and Experimental set up

It is hard to select a particular job specimen and corresponding cutting tool material from a huge range of standard materials. IS-6063 aluminum was chosen as a job specimen and it is ductile and can be easily machined by CNC lathe at high spindle speed. Fig. 1, and 2 shows the CNC machine, CNC machining set up. Surface roughness is measured by Tally-surf and tool wear rate by weighing machine of least count 10^{-3} . The Boron-carbide tool has been used as a tool for the operation.

Fig.1 CNC Machine

Fig.2 Experimental set up of CNC Machine

2.1. Cutting Fluid in CNC

Cutting fluid is a type of coolant and lubricant designed specifically for metalworking processes, such as machining and stamping. There are various kinds of cutting fluids, which include oils, oil-water emulsions, pastes, gels, aerosols (mists), and air or other gases. They may be made from petroleum distillates, animal fats, plant oils, water and air, or other raw ingredients. Depending on context and on which type of cutting fluid is being considered, it may be referred to as cutting fluid, cutting oil, cutting compound, coolant, or lubricant. Most metalworking and machining processes can benefit from the use of cutting fluid, depending on work piece material. Common exceptions to this are cast iron and brass, which may be machined dry (though this is not true of all brasses and any machining of brass will likely benefit from the presence of a cutting fluid).

Besides cooling, cutting fluids also aid the cutting process by lubricating the interface between the tool's cutting edge and the chip. By preventing friction at this interface, some of the heat generation is prevented. This lubrication also helps prevent the chips from being welded onto the tool, which would interfere with subsequent cutting.

Metal cutting generates heat due to friction and energy lost deforming the material. The surrounding air has low thermal conductivity (conducts heat poorly) meaning it is a poor coolant. Production work requires heavy cutting over long time periods and typically produces more heat than air cooling can remove. Rather than pausing production while the tool cools, using liquid coolant removes significantly more heat more rapidly, and can also speed cutting and reduce friction and tool wear. However, it is not just the tool which heats up but also the work surface. Excessive temperature in the tool or work surface can ruin the temper of both, soften either to the point of uselessness or failure, burn adjacent material, create unwanted thermal expansion or lead to unwanted chemical reactions such as oxidation.

2.2 ADVANTAGE OF USING COOLANT IN CNC

Two-thirds of the heat is generated as a by-product of shearing off the work piece material. The other one-third is created by the friction of the chip sliding over the cutting tool.

- Chip clearing: 80 % of the heat generated is carried away by chips. Spraying a liquid at the cut helps move the chips out of the way of the cutter so it doesn't have to recut the chips or use valuable chip clearance on chips that are not part of the current cut. Re-cutting chips destroys surface finish and dulls tools much more quickly. In the worst case, a cutter down in a slot or hole can get clogged with chips and get much hotter or even break.
- Lubrication: Some materials, like aluminium or some steels are sticky. They have an affinity for the material cutters are made from and will try to weld them to the cutter unless we can arrange for some lubrication to make that makes things slippery so the chips are less likely to adhere.
- Cooling: Liquids, especially water-soluble coolants, are capable of carrying heat away from the cut much more efficiently than air.

2.3 PROPERTIES OF ALUMINIUM 6063 ALLOY

The material selected for this operation is Aluminium 6063 plate which is commonly used alloy for several household appliances and industrial uses. It is the soft material and its surface roughness is comparatively higher. It is mainly used for moulding complex shapes. Some of the

main applications of aluminium 6063 are roof tops, window frames etc... Comparatively Al6061 and Al6082 have higher strength than Al6063. The thermal properties of Al6063 are shown in Table 1. Its Chemical compositions are shown in Table 2.

Table-1 the thermal properties of Al6063

Thermal properties	Composition
Melting onset (Solidus)	620 °C (1150 °F)
Specific heat capacity	900 J/kg-k
Thermal conductivity	200w/m-k
Thermal diffusivity	82m ² /s

Table 2 Chemical compositions of Al 6063

Material properties	Composition
Base metal price	16% rel
Density	2.7 g/cm ³ (170lb/ft ³)
Strength to weight ratio	93kN-m/kg
Physical properties	Composition
Electrical conductivity	53% IACS
Calomel potential	740 mV
Electrical resistivity order of magnitude	7 10 ^x Ω-m

3. Experimental results analysis based on RSM

Table 3 represents the process parameters and their levels as per the central composite design of experiments (DOE).

Table3-the process parameters and their levels

Variable	levels		
Spindle speed	1500	1750	2100
Depth of cut	0.15	0.35	0.55
Feed rate	30	40	50

3.1 Development of mathematical models and ANOVA Test

Mathematical models have been established as non-linear complex models by co-relating the machining responses with the regression coefficient and analysis of variances has been performed for verified the fitness of models as well as fitness and validation of test results. Equation 1, 2 show the developed models for surface roughness and tool wear rate respectively. Table4 and 5 represent their ANOVA table.

$$Y(Ra) = 1.17321 - 0.27310x_1 + 0.20800x_2 + 0.05520x_3 + 0.02773 x_1^2 + 0.11223x_2^2 - 0.12077x_3^2 - 0.10400x_1x_2 - 0.01275x_1x_3 - 0.02175 x_2x_3$$

(1)

Table4 Analysis of variances (ANOVA) Table for Surface Roughness

SOURCE	DOF	SS	MS	F	P
Regression	9	1.35756	0.150840	32.93	0.000
Linear	3	0.05700	0.019001	87.98	0.000
Square	3	0.05700	0.019001	4.15	0.038
Interaction	3	0.09161	0.030538	6.67	0.009
Residual Error	10	0.04580	0.004580		
Lack – of - Fit	5	0.03201	0.006401	2.32	0.189
Pure Error	5	0.01380	0.002760		
TOTAL	19				

$$R^2 = 96.74\%, \text{adj } R^2 = 93.8\%$$

From the above table 1 it is clear that the R^2 , as well as adjusted R^2 value for both cases, are near about 95% confidence level which validated the test results and developed non-linear models and the F, ratio test value is less than 4.06 for 5 degrees of freedom (DOF) for the lack of fit and also the P, value is also very less, so the tested results meets the models.

3.2 Parametric influences on machining characteristics

3.2.1 Influence of spindle speed, depth of cut and feed rate during stepped turning on surface roughness

From the figure 3 and 4 it is clear that if spindle speed is increased surface roughness of work specimen is decreased but for increasing of machining depth and feed rate, surface roughness increases because the contraction between tool and job is increased and irregularities on the workpiece becomes more but if the spindle speed is higher, cutting force as well as cutting speed becomes higher, so as that material is removed with high precession as well as maintaining the accuracy and then surface roughness becomes lower.

Fig. 3 Effects of cutting speed and depth of cut on surface roughness (R_a)

Fig.4 Effects of feed rate and depth of cut on surface roughness (R_a)

3.3 Optimization for minimum Surface roughness (R_a)

For finding the desirability of the developed model near about 1 and to achieve the parametric combination for the minimum surface roughness, is shown in figure 8 and minimum surface roughness is achieved $0.7294\mu\text{m}$ at the parametric combination of $2100\text{ rpm}/0.2389\text{mm}/30\text{mmmin}^{-1}$ by single objective optimization using desirability function analysis of Response Surface Methodology (RSM). Figure 6 shows the Multi-objective optimization for minimum surface roughness and tool wear rate during fabrication of miniature product.

Fig.5 Single objective optimization for surface roughness during fabrication of miniature product

Figure 7 shows the surface roughness plot for optimal conditions. Figure 8 shows the product which has been produced by CNC machine and the dimensions of that product. The optimum parameters that found from the modeling are 1525 rpm, 0.15 mm, and 30 mm min⁻¹ for cutting speed, depth of cut, and feed rate respectively .

Fig.6 Multi-objective optimization for minimum surface roughness and tool wear rate during fabrication of miniature product

Figure 7 Surface Roughness plot for optimal conditions

Fig.8 Fabrication of miniature product of IS-6063 Aluminum using CNC programming at 1525rpm/0.15mm/30mm min⁻¹

4. Conclusions

To reach the goal and to fulfill the objective of the present research the following conclusions can be drawn-

- Developed mathematical models have been validated by the adequacy test (ANOVA).
- Minimum surface roughness is achieved 0.7294µm at the parametric combination of 2100 rpm/0.2389mm/30mmmin-1 by single objective optimization using desirability function analysis.
- Multi responses optimized for surface roughness = 1.0472 µm and TWR = 0.0210mg/hr at the parametric combination of 1525rpm/0.015mm/30mm min-1.
- Tiny product has been fabricated on IS-617 Aluminum successfully and stepped turning operations have been carried at 1525rpm/0.015mm/30mm min⁻¹.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [1] Kalpakjian, S. and Schmid, S. *Manufacturing Engineering and Technology*, 7th ed., Prentice Hall, New Jersey.
- [2] Ostwald, P.F. and Munoz, J. *Manufacturing Processes and Systems*, 9th ed., John Wiley and Sons, New Delhi, India.
- [3] Wang Z, Meng H and Fu J, Novel method for evaluating surface roughness by grey dynamic filtering. *Measurement*, 2010; 43 (1), 78–82.
- [4] Ahilan C, Somasundaram K, Sivakumaran N and Edwin R J D, Modeling and prediction of machining quality in CNC turning process using intelligent hybrid decision making tools. *Applied Soft Computing*, 2013; 13, 1543–1551.
- [5] Boothroyd G and Knight W A, *Fundamentals of Machining and Machine Tools*, Marcel-Dekker, New York 1989.
- [6] Abouluelatta OB and Madl J, Surface roughness prediction based on cutting parameters and tool vibrations in turning operations. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, 2001; 118, 269-277.
- [7] Upadhayay V, Jain P K and Mehta N K, In-process prediction of surface roughness in turning of Ti–6Al–4V alloy using cutting parameters and vibration signals. *Measurement*, 2013; 46, 154-160.
- [8] Tangjitsitcharoen S and Moriwak T, Intelligent monitoring and identification of cutting states of chips and chatter on CNC turning machine. *Journal of Manufacturing Processes* 2008; 10, 40-46.
- [9] Dhabale R, Jatti V K S and Singh TP, Multi-objective optimization of turning process during machining of AlMg1SiCu using non-dominated sorted genetic algorithm. *Procedia Materials Science* 2014; 6, 961-966.
- [10]. Palanikumar K, Karthikeyan R. Optimal machining conditions for turning of particulate metal matrix composites using Taguchi and response surface methodologies. *Machining Science and Technology, an International Journal*. 2007; 10: 417— 433.
- [11]. Sahin Yusuf, Motorcu AR. Surface roughness model for machining mild steel with coated carbide tool. *Materials and Design*. 2005; 26: 321-326.
- [12]. Noordin MY, Venkatesh VC, Sharif S, Elting S, Abdullah A. Application of response surface methodology in describing the performance of coated carbide tools when turning AISI 1045 steel. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*. 2004; 145: 46—58.
- [13]. Singh H. and Kumar P., (2006), “Optimizing Feed Force for Turned Parts through the Taguchi Technique”, *Sadhana*, Volume 31, Number 6, pp. 671–681.
- [14] Rao R V, Review of applications of TLBO algorithm and a tutorial for beginners to solve the unconstrained and constrained optimization problems. *Decision Science Letters* 2016; 5(1) 1-30.